

Fear of Missing Out, Narcissism, Emotional Regulation, and Social Networking Addiction among Social Networking Users

Dinesh Naik¹ and Shubham Sherekar²

Department of Psychology, NVPM's Arts, Commerce & Science College, Lasalgaon, Nashik, Maharashtra¹

Department of Psychology, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Ganeshkhind, Pune, Maharashtra²

The aim of the present research was to study fear of missing out (FOMO), narcissism, emotional regulation and social networking addiction among social networking sites (SNS) users which includes Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, etc. The sample ($N=64$) of SNS users was collected from Pune city through the purposive sampling technique. The sample used in this research ranged from 17 to 21 years (mean age=18.89 years). The tools used in this research were the Fear of Missing out Scale (FoMO) by Przybylski et al. (2013); the Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI-16) by Daniel Ames et al. (2006); Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) by Gross et al. (2003); and Social Networking Addiction Scale by Shahnawaz, Ganguly, and Zou. The findings showed that impulsivity was positively correlated with fear of missing out as a characteristic of social networking addiction ($r=0.314, p < 0.05$). Also, impulsivity was positively correlated with narcissism ($r=0.261, p < 0.05$). Impulsivity and cognitive reappraisal were negatively correlated with each other ($r = -0.277, p < 0.05$). Social networking addiction and fear of missing out were positively correlated with each other ($r=0.254, p < 0.05$). Also, social networking addiction and cognitive reappraisal negatively correlated with each other ($r = -0.286, p < 0.05$). Further, the regression analysis shows that fear of missing out predicts 9.8 % of impulsivity in social networking addiction (r square= 0.098). Fear of missing out and cognitive reappraisal together predicted 19 % of impulsivity in social networking addiction (r square= 0.190).

Keywords: fear of missing out (FOMO), narcissism, emotional regulation, social networking sites (SNS) users

The present study was an effort to study the fear of missing out (FOMO), narcissism, emotional regulation, and social networking addiction among social networking sites (SNS) users. The study looks at impulsivity, virtual freedom, and negative outcome as aspects of social networking addiction, as well as fear of missing out, narcissism, and expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal as two aspects of emotional regulation technique. Problematic internet or social networking use has become a serious health problem. This study explores the personality aspects of young social networking users. The implication of this research would be consideration of teenagers' mental health, being an adolescent, how they are getting addicted to social networking sites and ultimately their mental health is getting affected. So, there is a very important need to emphasize more the effects of social networking on youth's mental health.

The study explores the concepts of fear of missing out (FOMO), narcissism, emotional regulation, and social networking addiction among social networking sites (SNS) users.

SNS' Problematic Use

In the last few years, people have joined Twitter, Instagram, and

Author Note

¹Dr. Dinesh Naik, Department of Psychology, NVPM's Arts Commerce & Science College, Lasalgaon, Nashik, Maharashtra
²Shubham Sherekar, Department of Psychology, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Ganeshkhind, Pune, Maharashtra

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Dinesh Naik, Department of Psychology, NVPM's Arts Commerce & Science College, Lasalgaon, Nashik, Maharashtra
E-mail: dr_dineshnaik@yahoo.co.in

Facebook to engage with like-minded people, and social networking sites have grown tremendously. For many individuals, social networking has become a favorite pastime activity since it allows them to communicate with each other regardless of the time or place. (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). Facebook emerged in 2014 and shortly became the largest social network site. As of the second quarter of 2020, Facebook had over 270 million monthly active users throughout the world, according to the site (Facebook, 2020). Similarly, other social networking sites like Instagram, WhatsApp, and Twitter gained popularity rapidly. Instagram has over 1 billion users worldwide. These social networking applications/sites are also most popular among Indian users. India is the most populated country on Facebook, with approximately 310 million users. (Statista, 2020). People use social networking to connect with the world and express themselves on a virtual platform. People's lives have become increasingly dependent on social networking platforms. According to researchers, the perceived necessity to be online on social networking may trigger compulsive use of networking sites, which can lead to symptoms and outcomes such as tolerance, withdrawal, relapse, salience, and mood modification, which are generally associated with substance abuse (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). Literature suggests that uncontrolled and dysregulated use of SNS impacts the mental health of a person negatively (Pontes et al., 2018). Some symptoms of substance-related addiction can be seen in behavioral addiction (Marks, 1990). These symptoms include the symptoms related to substance addiction as mentioned above. Unrestricted and irresistible online social networking use in the recent past has been identified as a behavioral addiction (Andreassen, 2015).

Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)

The fear of missing out is "a pervasive apprehension that others

might be having rewarding experiences from which one is absent and a desire to stay continually connected with what others are doing" (Przybylski, Murayama, DeHaan, & Gladwell, 2013). In other words, a constant fear that other people are having pleasant experiences and the person is missing out on this experience. Researchers have suggested that FOMO is associated with social networking addiction (Yin et al., 2019). Although very few studies are available on this construct. In a recent study, FOMO was associated with smartphone addiction (Chotpitayusunondh & Douglas, 2016). Therefore, studying the role of fear of missing out in social networking addiction is needed.

Narcissism

In accord with research, personality plays a big role in SNS addiction. Individuals can connect with others via social media to their objectives and attainments with a large audience (Andreassen, Pallesen, & Griffiths, 2017). Also, they can receive more apparent rewards and acceptance or recognition from other SNS in the form of "likes" and confirmatory comments (Andreassen, Pallesen, & Griffiths, 2017). Narcissistic personality disorder, a pattern of narcissism that also is pathological, is a personality disorder marked by high levels of self-love, visions of eternal success, emotions of preciousness and uniqueness, apathy, jealousy, and egotism (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). This study is aimed to determine the association between narcissism and social networking addiction, rather than to measure pathological narcissism.

Emotion Regulation

"Emotion regulation" is an idiom that refers to a person's ability to properly control and respond to emotional experiences (Rolston & Lloyd-Richardson, 2017). Research has shown that problems in emotion regulation are present in alcohol, and substance addiction also (Estévez et al., 2017). Research evidence suggests that behavioral addiction and substance addiction has similar symptoms (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). Hence emotion regulation and social networking addiction are related to each other and needed to be studied more.

Method

Participants

The participants for this study were 64 undergraduate students (38 males, 26 females) who are SNS users from Pune City. The participants were regular users of one/all of the social networking sites/apps like Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter, etc. Age ranged from 17 to 21 years ($M=18.89$ years). Purposive sampling was done for this study.

Instruments

Social Networking Sites Addiction: SNAS was used to measure the problematic use/addiction of the participants in this study. SNAS is developed by Shahnawaz, Ganguli, and Zou (2013). The test contains 32 items. It has 3 factors: impulsivity, virtual freedom, and negative outcome. A higher score indicates higher SNS addiction.

Fear of Missing Out (FOMO): The fear of missing out scale (Przybylski, Murayama, DeHann, & Gladwell, 2013) was used for measuring the fear of missing out. There are 10 items in this test. A higher score means higher fear of missing out.

Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI-16): Narcissistic

Personality Inventory (Ames et al., 2006) was used to measure narcissistic personality traits. This test contains 16 pairs of items among which the respondent has to choose any one of the two options.

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ): Emotion Regulation Questionnaire by Gross and John (2003) was used to measure Emotion regulation strategy (Gross et al., 2003). The test consists of ten items and two dimensions: cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression. A higher score indicates higher use of emotion regulation strategy.

The participants were asked to respond to the items by marking any one of the responses according to the response pattern of the respective tools. On the basis of the total score of subjects on various tests and scores on different dimensions/ factors, the data analysis was done.

Procedure

The 64 participants completed the questionnaires individually or in groups of four to five. Researchers were present to answer any queries participants had and to clarify items when needed. Participants' consent was taken before the data collection and all the instructions were explained properly.

Results

SPSS 21.0 for Windows was used to run the statistical standard procedures. To test relationships between two variables, Pearson correlations were computed. The data was found to be normal. Mean, Standard Deviations and correlations for narcissism, FOMO, and emotion management, as well as social networking addiction ($N=64$).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	M	SD	N
Impulsivity	48.42	9.624	64
Virtual Freedom	24.67	3.441	64
Negative Outcome	14.75	2.884	64
Social Networking Addiction Total	160.94	21.567	64
Fear of Missing out	25.67	6.937	64
Narcissism	5.94	3.380	64
Cognitive Reappraisal	46.88	9.894	64
Expressive Suppression	28.95	7.497	64
Emotion Regulation Total	17.92	4.739	64

Table 1 displays the sample's descriptive statistics. The total sample used for this study was $N= 64$ (38 males, 26 females). The age ranged from 17 to 21 years (mean age=18.89 years). The sample was analyzed on SPSS and it was found to be normal.

Further analysis was done on the data. Table 2 illustrates the correlations between the variables. Impulsivity as a dimension of social networking addiction was positively correlated with fear of missing out ($r= 0.314$) at a 0.05 level of significance. Also, impulsivity was positively correlated with narcissism ($r=0.261$) at a 0.05 level of significance. Impulsivity and cognitive reappraisal were negatively correlated with each other ($r=-0.277$) significant at a 0.05 level of significance. Social networking addictions and other variables were not associated with each other.

Table 2*Correlations*

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Impulsivity	1	.033	.301*	.943**	.314*	.261*	-.210	-.277*	.000
2 Virtual Freedom		1	-.085	.338**	-.203	-.081	-.165	-.133	-.134
3 Negative Outcome			1	.375**	.293*	.163	-.001	.027	-.046
4 Social Networking Addiction Total				1	.254*	.229	-.240	-.286*	-.049
5 Fear of Missing out					1	.229	.087	.080	.054
6 Narcissism						1	-.004	.057	-.097
7 Emotion Regulation Total							1	.887**	.684**
8 Cognitive Reappraisal								1	.271*
9 Expressive Suppression									1

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 3*Regression Analysis*

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.314 ^a	.098	.084	9.212	
2	.436 ^b	.190	.164	8.800	1.776

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), FM Total, b. Predictors: (Constant), FM Total, Cognitive Reappraisal, c. Dependent Variable: Impulsivity

Social networking addiction and fear of missing out were positively associated with each other ($r=0.254$) at a 0.05 level of significance. Also, social networking addiction and cognitive reappraisal negatively correlated with each other ($r= -0.286$) at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3 displays the regression analysis of the data. Impulsivity was considered as a criterion and fear of missing out and cognitive reappraisal were kept as predictors. The regression analysis shows that fear of missing out predicts 9.8 % of impulsivity in social networking addiction (r square= 0.098). Fear of missing out and cognitive reappraisal together predicted 19 % of impulsivity in social networking addiction.

Discussion

The present study aimed to explore fear of missing out (FOMO), narcissism, emotion regulation, and social networking addiction among social networking sites (SNS) users. The results obtained were interesting and mostly as hypothesized. According to the findings, impulsivity, fear of missing out, and narcissism all have a significant positive relationship. Also, impulsivity and cognitive reappraisal were negatively correlated with each other.

The study's major findings support the importance of fear of missing out in social networking usage. Social networking addiction and fear of missing out were significantly positively correlated with each other. In the regression analysis, it was found that fear of missing out was predicted at 9.8 % of impulsivity in social networking addiction and fear of missing out and cognitive reappraisal together were predicting 19 % of impulsivity in SNS addiction. This suggests that social networking addiction is linked to fear of missing out (FOMO), and that fear of missing out (fomo) might lead to impulsive SNS addiction. The finding illustrates that there is no association between narcissism and social networking

addiction together with emotion regulation.

The results matched those of a study done by Pontes, it was found that fear of missing out predicted social networking addiction significantly (Pontes et al., 2018). A total of 46% of the total variance in SNS addiction was predicted by fear of missing out, which is consistent with our findings. Additionally, Blackwell and others (2017) in their study found that fear of missing out and social media addiction were linked, and fomo was predicting social networking addiction (Blackwell et al., 2017). Furthermore, in a study "fear of missing out: testing relationships with negative affectivity, online social engagement, and problematic smartphone use" by Elhai et al. (2018) it was detected that fomo was associated with negative affectivity, social smartphone use, and the severity of problematic smartphone use. Social networking addiction and problematic smartphone usage are linked (Wu et al., 2013). Therefore we can assume that the fear of missing out is closely linked with social networking addiction.

Fox and others (2007) in their study of "difficulties in emotion regulation and impulse control during cocaine abstinence", found that cocaine addicts have trouble controlling their emotions, especially during early abstinence (Fox et al., 2007). This indicates the relationship between emotion regulation and addictions. Elhai and others (2018) in their research "depression and emotion regulation predict objective smartphone use measured over one week" observed that significant variation in objectively observed smartphone use has been associated with expressive suppression of emotions and depression (Elhai et al., 2018). These findings are consistent with our results indicating that social networking addiction and emotion regulation are correlated with each other.

Andreassen, Pallesen, and Griffiths (2017) in their study higher Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale scores were linked to having lower education, being a woman, being a student, not being in a

relationship, having lower self-esteem, lower age, having a lower income, and narcissism (Andreassen et al., 2017). Though in our findings narcissism was not significantly correlated with other variables, the research suggests that variables like lower age, and lower self-esteem are associated with emotion regulation (Fernandes, Newton, & Essau, 2021). Here we can note that social networking addiction and emotion regulation are associated with each other. Additionally, a study by Marino (2019) found that emotion regulation appears to be linked to youth's problematic internet use (Marino et al., 2019). This conclusion is also pertinent to our findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study showed a significant correlation between fear of missing out, narcissism, and cognitive reappraisal in social networking addiction, which can be further studied to understand the nature of behavioral addiction to social networking sites. The variables studied in this research were important facets of personality. This research explores the variables linked with social networking addiction and the nature of SNS addiction. It will be very interesting to study the mentioned variables on a larger sample.

References

- American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). Arlington, VA: Author.
- Ames, D. R., Rose, P., & Anderson, C. P. (2006). The NPI-16 as a short measure of narcissism. *Journal of Research in Personality, 40*(4), 440-450.
- Andreassen, C. (2015). *Online social network site addiction: A comprehensive review. current addiction reports, 2*. 10.1007/s40429-015-0056-9.
- Andreassen, C. S., Pallesen, S., & Griffiths, M. D. (2017). The relationship between addictive use of social media, narcissism, and self-esteem: Findings from a large national survey. *Addictive Behaviors, 64*, 287-293.
- Blackwell, D., Leaman, C., Tramosch, R., Osborne, C., & Liss, M. (2017). Extraversion, neuroticism, attachment style and fear of missing out as predictors of social media use and addiction. *Personality and Individual Differences, 116*, 69-72.
- Boustead, R., & Flack, M. (2021). Moderated-mediation analysis of problematic social networking use: The role of anxious attachment orientation, fear of missing out and satisfaction with life. *Addictive Behaviors, 119*, 106938.
- Chotpitayasunondh, V., & Douglas, K. M. (2018). Measuring phone snubbing behavior: Development and validation of the Generic Scale of Phubbing (GSP) and the Generic Scale of Being Phubbed (GSBP). *Computers in Human Behavior, 88*, 5-17.
- Elhai, J. D., Levine, J. C., Alghraibeh, A. M., Alafnan, A. A., Aldraiweesh, A. A., & Hall, B. J. (2018). Fear of missing out: Testing relationships with negative affectivity, online social engagement, and problematic smartphone use. *Computers in Human Behavior, 89*, 289-298.
- Elhai, J. D., Tiamiyu, M. F., Weeks, J. W., Levine, J. C., Picard, K. J., & Hall, B. J. (2018). Depression and emotion regulation predict objective smartphone use measured over one week. *Personality and Individual Differences, 133*, 21-28.
- Estévez, A. N. A., Jáuregui, P., Sánchez-Marcos, I., López-González, H., & Griffiths, M. D. (2017). Attachment and emotion regulation in substance addictions and behavioral addictions. *Journal of behavioral addictions, 6*(4), 534-544.
- Fioravanti, G., Casale, S., Benucci, S. B., Probstamo, A., Falone, A., Ricca, V., & Rotella, F. (2021). Fear of missing out and social networking sites use and abuse: A meta-analysis. *Computers in Human Behavior, 122*, 106839.
- Fox, H. C., Axelrod, S. R., Paliwal, P., Sleeper, J., & Sinha, R. (2007). Difficulties in emotion regulation and impulse control during cocaine abstinence. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence, 89*(2-3), 298-301.
- Fernandes, B., Newton, J., & Essau, C. A. (2022). The mediating effects of self-esteem on anxiety and emotion regulation. *Psychological Reports, 125*(2), 787-803.
- Gross, J.J., & John, O.P. (2003). Individual differences in two emotion regulation processes: Implications for affect, relationships, and well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 85*, 348-362.
- Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2017). Social networking sites and addiction: Ten lessons learned. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 14*(3), 311.
- Li, L., Niu, Z., Mei, S., & Griffiths, M. D. (2022). A network analysis approach to the relationship between fear of missing out (FoMO), smartphone addiction, and social networking site use among a sample of Chinese university students. *Computers in Human Behavior, 128*, 107086.
- Marino, C., Caselli, G., Lenzi, M., Monaci, M. G., Vieno, A., Nikčević, A. V., & Spada, M. M. (2019). Emotion regulation and desire thinking as predictors of problematic facebook use. *Psychiatric Quarterly, 90*(2), 405-411.
- Marks, I. (1990). Behavioural (non-chemical) addictions. *British Journal of Addiction, 85*(11), 1389-1394.
- Phan, T. T. H., & Vu, P. A. (2015). The impact of marketing mix elements on food buying behavior: A study of supermarket consumers in Vietnam. *International Journal of Business and Management, 10*(10), 206.
- Pontes, H. M., Taylor, M., & Stavropoulos, V. (2018). Beyond "facebook addiction": The role of cognitive-related factors and psychiatric distress in social networking site addiction. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking, 21*(4), 240-247. Doi:10.1089/cyber.2017.0609
- Przybylski, A. K., Murayama, K., DeHaan, C. R., & Gladwell, V. (2013). Motivational, emotional, and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out. *Computers in Human Behavior, 29*, 1814-1848.
- Rolston, A., & Lloyd-Richardson, E. (2017). *What is emotion regulation and how do we do it?* Cornell Research Program on Self-Injury and Recovery. [on-line]. [cit. 2017-22-09]
- Rozgonjuk, D., Sindermann, C., Elhai, J. D., & Montag, C. (2020). Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) and social media's impact on daily-life and productivity at work: Do WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat use disorders mediate that association? *Addictive Behaviors, 110*, 106487.
- Shahnawaz, M. G., Zou, M., & Ganguli, N. (2013). *Social Networking Addiction Scale (SNAS)*. New Delhi: Prasad Psycho Corporation.
- Spada, M. M., & Marino, C. (2017). Metacognitions and emotion regulation as predictors of problematic internet use in adolescents. *Clinical Neuropsychiatry, 14*(1), 59-63.
- Statista Facts on Social Networks (2017). Available online: <https://www.statista.com/topics/1164/socialnetworks/> (accessed on 13 January 2017).
- Wu, A. M., Cheung, V. I., Ku, L., & Hung, E. P. (2013). Psychological risk factors of addiction to social networking sites among Chinese smartphone users. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions, 2*(3), 160-166.
- Yin, L., Wang, P., Nie, J., Guo, J., Feng, J., & Lei, L. (2021). Social networking sites addiction and FoMO: The mediating role of envy and the moderating role of need to belong. *Current Psychology, 40*(8), 3879-3887.
- Yu, S., Wu, A. M. S., & Pesigan, I. J. A. (2016). Cognitive and psychosocial health risk factors of social networking addiction. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction, 14*(4), 550-564.

Received April 28, 2022

Revision received May 14, 2022

Accepted May 15, 2022